

ON MECHANICALLY COUPLED TAPERED LAMINATES WITH BALANCED PLAIN WEAVE AND NON-CRIMP FABRICS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents definitive stacking sequence listings for tapered, warp-free Balanced Plain Weave (BPW) and Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) laminate designs with and without *Extension-Shearing* and/or *Bending-Twisting* coupling behaviour. A multiple-ply termination algorithm is employed to develop permissible tapered designs in which consistent mechanical coupling characteristics and immunity to thermal warping distortion are preserved. Single ply terminations applied to NCF or BPW materials are equivalent to two adjacent ply terminations in traditional UD materials, and therefore introduce a constraint that may reduce the design space substantially, particularly in ‘thin laminate’ designs. The tapered designs investigated here range between ($n_{\text{NCF}} = n_{\text{BPW}} =$) 4 and 12 NCF or BPW plies; equivalent to between ($n_{\text{UD}} =$) 8 and 24 plies of UD material.

1 INTRODUCTION

A recent study on single-ply terminations [1] investigated the extent of the design space for tapered laminates when the ubiquitous balanced and/or symmetric design rules are relaxed. Consideration of design heuristics, involving ply contiguity (≤ 2), representing the most severe design constraints for tapered laminates, were found to significantly influenced the form of the designs, i.e., single ply terminations are possible only at the laminate mid-plane for consistent mechanically (de-)coupled characteristics. Nevertheless, this constraint may be desirable for mitigation of load path fluctuations and in-plane loading eccentricities. Several key observations were also made from the results presented: Tapered laminate solutions arise in non-symmetric, as well as symmetric laminates, with consistent mechanical behaviour and immunity to thermal warping throughout, for Simple laminate configurations as well as those with *Extension-Shearing* and/or *Bending-Twisting* coupling; Single cross-ply terminations are permissible in *Simple* or *Bending-Twisting* coupled laminates, but only within a mid-plane ply block, which can be non-symmetric; Single angle-ply terminations are permissible only in laminate configurations possessing *Extension-Shearing* and *Bending-Twisting* coupling and; Consistent mechanical *Extension-Shearing* and *Bending-Twisting* coupling can be preserved by modifying a mid-plane symmetric ply block, within an otherwise non-symmetric laminate configuration, which is applicable to both single angle-ply and/or cross-ply terminations. Most significantly, lamination parameter point clouds were found to reveal clear strings of points representing the tapered designs found, and demonstrating the potential for tailoring of stiffness properties through ply termination.

Similar tailoring strategies are now applied to balanced plain weave (BPW) and non-crimp fabric (NCF) laminate designs with single-ply or, where necessary, multiple-ply terminations, to investigate the extent to which individual layers can be terminated without introducing *Extension-Shearing* coupling, or to maintain *Extension-Shearing* throughout the tapered laminate.

With very few exceptions, tapered designs in aircraft construction are currently certified only for balanced and symmetric UD laminates [2], despite the severe design constraint that 1 angle-ply termination requires a further 3 angle-ply terminations: 2 terminations to maintain balanced angle-ply, and a further 2 to maintain symmetry. Balanced stacking sequences guarantee that *Extension-Shearing* coupling is eliminated by using matching pairs of angle-ply layers [3]. Symmetric laminates guarantee that coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane behaviour is eliminated, along with thermal warping distortions that would otherwise be expected. However, tapering of symmetric laminates with fewer than the requisite 4 angle-ply terminations is believed to be common in industrial practice [4], despite the fact that the effects on the structural integrity are not well understood; these effects are simply minimised by ensuring that terminations are made at the laminate mid-plane.

Recent research on laminate design has demonstrated that fully uncoupled laminates [5], or those with *Extension-Shearing* [3] and/or *Bending-Twisting* coupling [6,7] all have immunity to thermal warping distortion and, collectively, have a design space containing predominantly non-symmetric stacking sequences.

The results presented in this article are based on the four laminate classes, illustrated under free thermal contraction in Fig. 1. All are immune to thermal warping distortions by virtue of the fact that their coupling stiffness properties are null ($\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{0}$); as would be expected from symmetric laminate configurations. The first two classes contain balanced angle-ply layers, leading to uncoupled extensional stiffness properties. The *Simple* laminate in the first column is uncoupled in bending, whilst the laminate class in the second column possesses *Bending-Twisting* coupling. The final two laminate classes possess unbalanced angle-ply layers, leading to *Extension-Shearing* coupling properties. The laminate class in the third column is uncoupled in bending, whereas the laminate class in the fourth column has both *Extension-Shearing* and *Bending-Twisting* coupling, as would arise from unbalanced and symmetric laminates.

Figure 1 – In-plane thermal contraction responses (not to scale) resulting from a typical high temperature curing process. All examples shown are square, initially flat, composite laminates. The stacking sequences provided, in symbolic form, are representative of the minimum ply number grouping for each laminate class, with standard ply orientations ± 45 , 0 and 90° in place of symbols +, -, \circ and \bullet , respectively.

C-Ply[®] (bi-angle) non-crimp fabrics consist of two plies of carbon fibre, stitched together; one at 0° and the other at either a shallow angle (e.g. 20°) or the standard 45° ply angle considered here. Indeed, the new design solutions reported here, loosely follow the repeating bi-angle philosophy, $[0/\theta]_T$, which possess *Extension-Shearing* and *Bending-Twisting* dominant coupling, but now with immunity to thermal warping distortions; warping is eliminated in $[0/\theta]_T$ laminates only when the number (r) of repeats becomes very large.

The four design freedoms associated with the stacking sequences for standard UD laminate manufacture, with ply orientations 0, 90 and $\pm 45^\circ$, are increased to eight using 0/45 and 0/-45 bi-angle NCF: by flipping (-45/0 and 45/0), rotating (90/-45 and 90/45) or both (45/90 and -45/90). The underling helps to differentiate between 0/45 and 0/-45 plies.

The remainder of this article is arranged as follows. Section 2 provides a summary of the derivation of definitive listings for the warp free laminate classes given in Fig. 1. A ply termination algorithm is described in Section 3, which is then applied to the definitive listings of laminates from each of the four laminate classes to develop tapered laminate designs and compatible stacking sequences for single and multiple ply terminations. Lamination parameters are introduced to allow the available design space to be visually interrogated in Section 4. Finally, tapered laminate examples are also presented before conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2 Derivation of stacking sequences

The common feature relating the *Simple*, *Extension-Shearing* and/or *Bending-Twisting* coupled laminate classes is that all are decoupled, i.e. $B_{ij} = 0$; hence in-plane and out-of-plane behaviour are independent and can therefore be treated separately. The constitutive relations simplify as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ \text{Sym.} & & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ \text{Sym.} & & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where the elements of the stiffness matrices are derived from the well know relationships:

$$A_{ij} = \sum Q'_{ij}(z_k - z_{k-1})$$

$$B_{ij} = \sum Q'_{ij}(z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2)/2 = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$D_{ij} = \sum Q'_{ij}(z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3)/3$$

in which: the summations extend over all n plies; Q'_{ij} are the transformed reduced stiffnesses ($i, j = 1, 2, 6$) and; z_k represents the distance from the laminate mid-plane of the k^{th} ply.

In the derivation of the database of stacking sequences, which assumes (but is not restricted to) combinations of standard fibre angle orientations, i.e. 0, 90 and/or $\pm\theta^\circ$ ($= \pm 45^\circ$), the general rule of symmetry is relaxed. Neither cross plies nor angle plies are constrained to be symmetric about the laminate mid-plane. The derivation of the NCF laminates involved the added restrictions that each layer in the two-ply pairing: has identical orthotropic material properties; has identical thickness, t , and; differs only by its orientation, representing any combination of the eight pairings: 0/45, 0/-45, 45/0, 45/90, -45/0, -45/90, 90/45 and 90/-45. For BPW material, only two pairing constraints need to be imposed, i.e., 45/-45 and 0/90, since -45/45 and 90/0 give identical stiffness properties, respectively.

For compatibility with the previously published data, similar symbols have been adopted for defining all stacking sequences, i.e., \circ , \bullet , $+$ and $-$ are used in place of standard ply angle orientations 0, 90, $+45$ and -45° , respectively.

2.1 Non-dimensional parameters

Non-dimensional parameters allow the extensional and bending stiffness properties to be readily calculated for any fibre/matrix system and angle-ply orientation and provide a compact data set alongside each laminate stacking sequence derived.

The development of non-dimensional parameters involves the summations, for each ply orientation, of $(z_k - z_{k-1})$, $(z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2)$ and $(z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3)$, relating to the **A**, **B** and **D** matrices, respectively. Here, the distance from the laminate mid-plane, z , is expressed in terms of ply thickness t ; assumed to be unit value.

These non-dimensional parameters, together with the transformed reduced stiffness, Q'_{ij} , for each ply orientation of constant ply thickness, t , facilitate simple calculation of the elements of the extensional, coupling and bending stiffness matrices from:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{ij} &= \{n_+ Q'_{ij+} + n_- Q'_{ij-} + n_o Q'_{ijO} + n_\bullet Q'_{ij\bullet}\}t \\ B_{ij} &= 0 \\ D_{ij} &= \{\zeta_+ Q'_{ij+} + \zeta_- Q'_{ij-} + \zeta_o Q'_{ijO} + \zeta_\bullet Q'_{ij\bullet}\}t^3/12 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The *Extension-Shearing* and *Bending-Twisting* coupled (**A_FB₀D_F**) laminate satisfies the following non-dimensional parameter criteria:

$$\begin{aligned} n_+ &\neq n_- \\ \zeta_+ &\neq \zeta_- \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

whilst $n_+ = n_-$ and/or $\zeta_+ = \zeta_-$ are the conditions giving rise to the *Bending-Twisting* coupled and *Simple* or *Extension-Shearing* coupled laminate classes in Fig. 1, respectively.

The transformed reduced stiffnesses, Q'_{ij} , are defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} Q'_{11} &= Q_{11}\cos^4\theta + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\sin^2\theta + Q_{22}\sin^4\theta \\ Q'_{12} &= Q'_{21} = (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 4Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\sin^2\theta + Q_{12}(\cos^4\theta + \sin^4\theta) \\ Q'_{16} &= Q'_{61} = \{(Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta + (Q_{12} - Q_{22} + 2Q_{66})\sin^2\theta\}\cos\theta\sin\theta \\ Q'_{22} &= Q_{11}\sin^4\theta + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\sin^2\theta + Q_{22}\cos^4\theta \\ Q'_{26} &= Q'_{62} = \{(Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\sin^2\theta + (Q_{12} - Q_{22} + 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\}\cos\theta\sin\theta \\ Q'_{66} &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\sin^2\theta + Q_{66}(\cos^4\theta + \sin^4\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

and the reduced stiffness terms, Q_{ij} , are calculated from the orthotropic material properties:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= E_1/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ Q_{12} &= \nu_{12}E_2/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ Q_{22} &= E_2/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ Q_{66} &= G_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Note that orthotropic material properties imply that $Q_{16} = Q_{26} = 0$.

Lamination parameters, originally conceived by Tsai and Hahn [8] offer an alternative set of non-dimensional expressions when ply angles are a design constraint. They were first applied to optimum design by Miki [9] and presented in graphical form by Fukunaga and Vanderplaats [10]. Optimized lamination parameters may be matched against a corresponding set of stacking sequences. Graphical representations help with this design process, since arguably the greatest challenge to the composite

laminates designer, is the inverse problem of generating practical laminate configurations, which satisfy the optimized lamination parameters.

Elements of the extensional (**A**) and bending (**D**) stiffness matrices are each related to lamination parameters, ξ_i , and laminate invariants, U_i , respectively, by:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11} &= \{U_1 + \xi_1 U_2 + \xi_2 U_3\} \times H \\ A_{12} = A_{21} &= \{-\xi_2 U_3 + U_4\} \times H \\ A_{16} = A_{61} &= \{\xi_3 U_2/2 + \xi_4 U_3\} \times H \\ A_{22} &= \{U_1 - \xi_1 U_2 + \xi_2 U_3\} \times H \\ A_{26} = A_{62} &= \{\xi_3 U_2/2 - \xi_4 U_3\} \times H \\ A_{66} &= \{-\xi_2 U_3 + U_5\} \times H \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11} &= \{U_1 + \xi_9 U_2 + \xi_{10} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ D_{12} = D_{21} &= \{U_4 - \xi_{10} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ D_{16} = D_{61} &= \{\xi_{11} U_2/2 + \xi_{12} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ D_{22} &= \{U_1 - \xi_9 U_2 + \xi_{10} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ D_{26} = D_{62} &= \{\xi_{11} U_2/2 - \xi_{12} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ D_{66} &= \{-\xi_{10} U_3 + U_5\} \times H^3/12 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where the laminate thickness H (= number of plies, n , \times constant ply thickness, t) and the laminate invariants, U_i , are calculated from the reduced stiffness terms, Q_{ij} , of Eq. (6):

$$\begin{aligned} U_1 &= \{3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}\}/8 \\ U_2 &= \{Q_{11} - Q_{22}\}/2 \\ U_3 &= \{Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}\}/8 \\ U_4 &= \{Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}\}/8 \\ U_5 &= \{Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}\}/8 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

These ply orientation dependent lamination parameters are also related to the non-dimensional parameters, used in Eq. (3), by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1 &= \{n_+ \cos(2\theta_+) + n_- \cos(2\theta_-) + n_o \cos(2\theta_o) + n_{\bullet} \cos(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n \\ \xi_2 &= \{n_+ \cos(4\theta_+) + n_- \cos(4\theta_-) + n_o \cos(4\theta_o) + n_{\bullet} \cos(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n \\ \xi_3 &= \{n_+ \sin(2\theta_+) + n_- \sin(2\theta_-) + n_o \sin(2\theta_o) + n_{\bullet} \sin(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n \\ \xi_4 &= \{n_+ \sin(4\theta_+) + n_- \sin(4\theta_-) + n_o \sin(4\theta_o) + n_{\bullet} \sin(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_9 &= \{\zeta_+ \cos(2\theta_+) + \zeta_- \cos(2\theta_-) + \zeta_o \cos(2\theta_o) + \zeta_{\bullet} \cos(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^3 \\ \xi_{10} &= \{\zeta_+ \cos(4\theta_+) + \zeta_- \cos(4\theta_-) + \zeta_o \cos(4\theta_o) + \zeta_{\bullet} \cos(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^3 \\ \xi_{11} &= \{\zeta_+ \sin(2\theta_+) + \zeta_- \sin(2\theta_-) + \zeta_o \sin(2\theta_o) + \zeta_{\bullet} \sin(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^3 \\ \xi_{12} &= \{\zeta_+ \sin(4\theta_+) + \zeta_- \sin(4\theta_-) + \zeta_o \sin(4\theta_o) + \zeta_{\bullet} \sin(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^3 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Noting that for standard ply orientations 0, 90 and $\pm 45^\circ$, assumed here, $\xi_4 = \xi_{12} = 0$. There are further simplifications for BPW material [11], i.e.,

$$E_1 = E_2 = 0, \quad (12)$$

hence

$$U_2 = 0. \quad (13)$$

3. LAMINATE TAPERING ALGORITHM

Tapered laminates are certified for symmetric laminate construction, the majority of which possess *Bending-Twisting* coupling, but such designs have a severe design constraint, i.e., a single angle-ply termination requires a further three angle-ply terminations to maintain balanced and symmetric construction. This section investigates the extent to which this restriction can be overcome by employing NCF or balanced plain weave material without changing the mechanical behaviour or introducing undesirable warping distortions. Note, however, that neither single-ply nor multiple-ply taper is possible for *Extension-Shearing* coupled laminates within the range of ply number groupings previously investigated.

Tapered laminate designs have been developed in a two stage process. The first stage can be described as a top down process, in which each ply number grouping n is algorithmically filtered through ply number grouping $n-m$, representing m ply terminations.

A second stage, which can be described as a bottom up process, begins with compatible stacking sequences representing the minimum ply number grouping of interest. These sequences are then algorithmically filtered through higher ply number groupings, in turn, but now only sequences compatible with the minimum ply number grouping are retained.

The first stage of the termination scheme is not shown, but involves: m ply terminations, applied in turn to individual plies of every stacking sequence with n -ply layers of either NCF or balanced plain weave material; comparison with all stacking sequences with $n-m$ plies and; recording exact matches. The first (or upper surface) ply is assumed to be continuous throughout the tapering process; this represents a practical design constraint to prevent surface ply delamination. This constraint also applies to the last (or lower surface) ply for practical design, but the results have been reported here to reveal the propensity for such terminations. This gives rise to a higher combination of ply terminations, which increase by the factorial relationship:

$$(n-1)!/m!(n-1-m)! \quad (14)$$

Repeated sequences are removed from the data when multiple matches arise from different ply terminations within a single stacking sequence. This forms a starting point for the second stage of the tapering algorithm.

The second stage of the tapering algorithm can be described as a bottom up process, and begins with compatible stacking sequences representing the minimum ply number grouping (n) of interest. These sequences are then algorithmically filtered through higher ply number groupings, in turn, but now only sequences compatible with the minimum ply number grouping are retained. As in the first stage, the m ply termination scheme involves the removal of individual plies, in turn, for each stacking sequence with $n+m$ plies, and a comparison made against each stacking sequence with n plies, and matches recorded. This procedure ensures that all solutions reported here will be compatible with higher ply number groupings beyond those reported here. The number of ply terminations, m , varies with between NCF and balanced plain weave and depends on the form of the class of laminate being interrogated.

Details of the definitive list of BPW laminates [11] are repeated in Table 1, whereas the newly derived definitive list for NCF laminates are presented in Table 2. Table 1 reveals that tapering can be achieved with single ply terminations for Balanced Plain Weave (BPW) material, whereas Table 2 reveals that two NCF ply terminations are required for laminates with *Extension-Shearing* and

Bending-Twisting coupling and four NCF ply terminations are required for *Simple* and *Bending-Twisting* coupled laminates.

Table 1: Number of BPW laminate solutions for *Simple* ($A_S B_0 D_S$), *Bending-Twisting* coupled ($A_S B_0 D_F$) and *Extension-Shearing* and *Bending-Twisting* coupled ($A_F B_0 D_F$) warp-free laminate classes corresponding to, n_{BPW} , with BTW layers and equivalent number, n_{UD} , with UD layers.

(1) $N_{BPW}(n_{UD})$	(2) $A_S B_0 D_S$	(3) $A_S B_0 D_F$	(4) $A_F B_0 D_F$
4(8)	2	1	1
5(10)	4	–	4
6(12)	4	–	4
7(14)	10	–	10
8(16)	9	3	6
9(18)	26	–	26
10(20)	24	–	24
11(22)	76	–	76
12(24)	69	28	41

Table 2: Number of NCF laminate solutions for *Simple* ($A_S B_0 D_S$), *Bending-Twisting* coupled ($A_S B_0 D_F$) and *Extension-Shearing* and *Bending-Twisting* coupled ($A_F B_0 D_F$) warp-free laminate classes corresponding to, n_{NCF} , with NCF layers and equivalent number, n_{UD} , with UD layers.

(1) $N_{NCF}(n_{UD})$	(2) $A_S B_0 D_S$	(3) $A_S B_0 D_F$	(4) $A_F B_0 D_F$
4(8)	–	4	5
5(10)	–	–	–
6(12)	–	–	88
7(14)	–	–	–
8(16)	35	419	683
9(18)	–	–	–
10(20)	–	–	22,568
11(22)	–	–	–
12(24)	2,414	243,498	356,242

4. TAPERED LAMINATE DESIGNS

Lamination parameters permit an interrogation of the extent of resulting design space for the definitive listing of Tables 1 and 2 and the tapered laminate designs after applying the tapering algorithm, since individual laminate stacking sequences can now be represented by a single point in either a 2- or 3-dimensional space; for either or both the extensional stiffness properties and the bending stiffness properties. Each point, within the resulting point cloud, defines a co-ordinate set, from which the stiffness properties may be readily determined using Eq. (7) or Eq. (8).

This section compares the complete design spaces resulting from the summations of column (4) in Table 2 with the tapered solutions given in column (4) of Table 3. The comparisons are presented in Figs. 2 and 3. As a result of the constraint imposed by the NCF architecture, the design space for *Extension-Shearing* and *Bending-Twisting* coupled laminates is found to be substantially reduced in comparison to the equivalent UD design space, reported previously [6].

Figure 2 – Lamination parameter design spaces for $\mathbf{A}_F\mathbf{B}_0\mathbf{D}_F$ NCF laminates with up to $n_{\text{NCF}} = 12$ ($n_{\text{UD}} = 24$), corresponding to the results of Table 2 for: (a) plan view, (b) front elevation and (c) side elevation of the three dimensional bending stiffness coordinates, represented by ξ_9 , ξ_{10} , ξ_{11} . and; (d) front elevation of the two dimensional extensional stiffness coordinates, represented by ξ_1 , ξ_3 ($\xi_2 = 0$).

Table 3 – Number of *tapered* NCF laminate solutions for *Simple* ($\mathbf{A}_S\mathbf{B}_0\mathbf{D}_S$), *Bending-Twisting* coupled ($\mathbf{A}_S\mathbf{B}_0\mathbf{D}_F$) and *Extension-Shearing* and *Bending-Twisting* coupled ($\mathbf{A}_F\mathbf{B}_0\mathbf{D}_F$) warp-free laminate classes corresponding to, n_{NCF} , with NCF layers and equivalent number, n_{UD} , with UD layers.

(1) $N_{\text{NCF}}(n_{\text{UD}})$	(2) $\mathbf{A}_S\mathbf{B}_0\mathbf{D}_S$	(3) $\mathbf{A}_S\mathbf{B}_0\mathbf{D}_F$	(4) $\mathbf{A}_F\mathbf{B}_0\mathbf{D}_F$
4(8)	–	4	5
5(10)	–	–	–
6(12)	–	–	68
7(14)	–	–	–
8(16)	35	370	503
9(18)	–	–	–
10(20)	–	–	6,732
11(22)	–	–	–
12(24)	309	97,103	58,058

Figure 3 – Lamination parameter design spaces for *tapered* $A_F B_0 D_F$ NCF laminates with $n_{NCF} = 4-6-8-10$ ($\equiv n_{UD} = 8-12-16-20$), corresponding to the results of Table 2 for: (a) the two dimensional extensional stiffness coordinates, represented by ξ_1, ξ_2 and; (b) the two dimensional bending stiffness coordinates, represented by ξ_9, ξ_{10} .

Similar lamination parameter design spaces may be generated for the BPW material, but are omitted here, since all *Simple* laminates are constrained to a single line trajectory within a two dimensional design space; representing laminates with equal 0/90 and +45/-45 combinations. The coupled laminate classes, presented in columns (3) and (4) of Table 1, are achieved by off-axis alignment of the *Simple* laminate designs, for which $\xi_4, \xi_{12} \neq 0$; the design spaces are no longer constrained to the 2- and 3-dimensional representations as illustrated in Figs 2 and 3.

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